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Membrane processes – contemporary relevance & prospects

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Introduction: Membrane mediated separation is a versatile unit operation that can be used at various stages of product recovery for separation, concentration or purification of products. Membrane science is a highly interdisciplinary field, comprising of engineering, material science as well as chemistry. Over the last few decades, membranes have grown from a basic laboratory tool to a large scale industrial tool. Applications include desalination of sea water, removal of cells or cell debris, protein concentration, removal of virus, purification of food and pharmaceutical products. Nevertheless, membranes are the cardinal components of artificial organs, drug delivery and energy conversion devices. In this study, separation aspects of membranes through bulk liquid membrane set up have been demonstrated. Furthermore, the recovery potential for organic acids recovery from dilute solutions in lab and from a fermentation medium has been reviewed.

Methods: Experiments were carried out in a customized glass vessel consisting of 2 concentric cylinders joined from base. Inner cylinder carried the strip phase and the outer cylinder carried the feed phase. Organic LM was poured over two aqueous phases. The experiments were performed under stirring conditions. A range of feed and strip phase solutions along with different extractant concentrations have been used.

Results & Discussions: Separation potential of a bulk liquid membrane comprising of chemical species so as to recover organic acids from their dilute solutions was investigated. The BLM was made up of 2 aqueous phases and one organic phase comprised of an extractant. Recovery of acids upto 40% could be achieved for organic acids such as propionic acid, acetic acid and fumaric acid. It is speculated that these recoveries were based on reactive extraction process.

Conclusions: Successful energy efficient separations were achieved using the concept of BLM and the reactive extraction mechanism. Best separations were accomplished with enhanced carrier and strip phase concentrations. Further, careful selection of extractant chemistry with optimization of other parameters shall prove to be helpful for achieving substantial separations of given species.

Keywords: *Liquid membranes, Reactive extraction, Separation, membrane assisted process*

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